

The Unjournal

Evaluation 1 of "Does Conservation Work in General Equilibrium"

Evaluator 1

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ABSTRACT

[Here we will include the ~75 word, 400 character summary that we will request evaluators to provide. Otherwise, we will use an LLM-generated summary (and note this is the case).]

[Here, we offer a template for hosting Unjournal evaluations in PubPub, version 6. This template can also be used for sharing with authors (as a draft), for their response, before the full package is released.]

[To proceed...¹]

Footnotes

1. Create a new 'pub', import evaluator's content, copy in the material below, filling in as necessary, and checking/adjusting to maintain the desired formatting. 'Pub settings' will need adjusting. Pub settings will also need to be configured. See our internal Coda documentation. [↔](#)